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Review Article

Alopecia Areata: Pathophysiology, Current Treatments, and The Emerging Role of Herbal Remedies

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ABSTRACT

Hair is a keratinized epithelial structure, provides defense against exposure to sunlight. The anagen, catagen and telogen phases are the successive cycles that the hair growth goes through. An autoimmune disease called alopecia areata occurs when there is early transition of hair growth phase from anagen to the catagen, telogen, and exogen phase and results in hair loss. This review paper includes hair physiology, alopecia areata pathophysiology and herbal plants potential of alopecia areata over allopathic treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Keratinization of germinative cells results in better epithelial structure, which is what is known as hair, that provides the scalp with the best defense against exposure to sunlight [1, 2]. It serves as the body's protective appendages and is regarded as an integumentary accessory structure, together with sweat and sebaceous glands. Chemical components, including carbon, nitrogen and oxygen, combine with keratin to form hair [3]. Human existence is significantly impacted by hair, which serves as a statement of pride. Having beautiful, healthy hair is crucial to one's image [2,

15]. Although each person's hair grows differently, on average, it grows 15-30 mm every month [1].

An autoimmune disease called alopecia areata causes variable hair loss on scalp, face or body, which significantly lowers quality of life [7, 8, 23]. Non-scarring type hair loss is the second most prevalent form [7]. Worldwide, the disease's lifetime incidence is 2% and its prevalence is 1 in 1000 [16]. In 75% of cases of alopecia areata, the scalp's bald lesions are concentrated in one or more localized patches. Eye lashes and eyebrows may be affected by more widespread hair loss [17].

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Although alopecia areata frequently causes psychological distress, it is not a life-threatening condition [7, 18, 19, 20]. Chronic conditions include lupus erythematosus, vitiligo, autoimmune hemolytic anemia, atopic dermatitis, thallium acetate poisoning, hormonal changes and thyroid illness are frequently linked to alopecia areata [7, 9, 21]. Moreover, ocular and nail disorders may be linked to alopecia areata [22]. Although in alopecia areata the leukocyte-mediated inflammation was discovered almost a hundred years ago, the immune system's role in the pathophysiology of the condition has only been acknowledged as the main underlying cause since the late 1950s [7,9,24,25].

DIAGNOSIS:

Alopecia areata can influence any skin that bears hair, however, it usually influences the scalp first [9]. A well-defined bald patch free of itching, redness, peeling or scarring is the common clinical investigation of alopecia areata [7, 26]. Eight questions in the Alopecia Areata diagnostic form are used to separate patients with alopecia areata [7]. The instrument's specificity is 97.8%, and its sensitivity is 89.9% [7, 27]. In roughly 10% to 15% of instances, alopecia areata can affect the nails; in certain populations, it can affect up to 44% [9, 28, 29, 30]. If alopecia areata's clinical manifestation is unclear, a punch biopsy is performed [7].

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY:

The anagen, catagen, telogen phase are the successive cycles that the hair growth goes through [4, 12]. The primary factor influencing hair length is the anagen phase, lasts for two to six years on average. 85% of hair follicles on the scalp are in the anagen phase. When the growing cycle ends and a follicle starts to become dormant, the anagen phase is followed by a brief resting phase

known as catagen [4, 5, 13, 14]. The catagen phase lasts 10-14 days. When the hairs enter the telogen phase, they go into a resting state. For 90-100 days, this period lasts [6, 10, 11]. 15% of hair follicles on the scalp are in the telogen phase [5].

The early transition of hair follicles from the anagen phase into the catagen, telogen, and exogen phase results in alopecia areata and causes a decrease in hair growth and a rise in hair fall. It is crucial to remember that the cause of alopecia areata, like any autoimmune disease, is complex [32].

Factor	Explanation
Genetic Factor	Concerning the hereditary predisposition to alopecia areata; Class II Human Leukocyte Antigen (HLA-D) gene (region on human chromosome 6) [9, 31, 33, 34].
Concomitant Factors	Multiple concomitant disorders are linked to alopecia areata, which includes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thyroid disease • Vitiligo • Lupus erythematosus • Psychiatric disorders [2,9,35-41]
Oxidative Stress	There is higher levels of Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) antioxidant activity in the blood of alopecia areata patient [9, 42].
Vasculative System	Generally speaking, inflammation is frequently linked to increased blood flow to the affected areas. Lesions of alopecia areata exhibit elevated temperature, attributed to increased vascularization [9,43].
Environmental Factors	Many triggers variables have been suggested to be responsible for the commencement of an alopecia episode. Most often, it is described as either physical or emotional stress [9, 36, 44].

Alopecia areata's precise pathophysiology is not fully known [32]. The collapse of immunological

privilege is thought to be the cause of alopecia areata [31, 45]. Our body has immune privilege in a number of cells and organs, including testes, eyes and central nervous system [32]. Hair follicles also possess immune privilege, as evidenced by their immune privilege site and low expression levels of Major Histocompatibility Complex (MHC) [31, 32, 46]. Immune privilege is thought to be associated with low levels of Major Histocompatibility Complex 1 (MHC 1) and MHC 2 expression in hair follicles, results in loss of this immunological privilege. It was discovered that NKG2D, an activating receptor frequently linked to the natural killer (NK) cell lineage, was expressed by CD8⁺ T cells in close proximity to

the hair follicle. In the cell-transfer murine model of AA, it was discovered that this population of CD8⁺ NKG2D⁺ T cells was adequate for causing illness. Pro-inflammatory cytokines like IFN γ , which are strongly produced by activated CD8⁺ T cells, tilt the microenvironment of hair follicles in favor of inflammation [80]. Major Histocompatibility Complex expression is stimulated by interferon gamma, which also enables the follicle's secreted antigen to be delivered to T cells. The antigen hair follicles damaged by interleukin 15 (IL-15), which causes the regulatory T cells to be suppressed and CD8⁺ T cells to proliferate. This cause the follicles to accelerate into the catagen phase [32].

Fig.1. Pathophysiology of Alopecia Areata [32]

MANAGEMENT:

i) Drug Therapy

There are various drug therapies to treat alopecia areata. All therapies for alopecia areata focus on reducing hair loss and encouraging re-growth

because there is no solution for the underlying issues. Additionally, because alopecia areata progresses in an unpredictable manner, treatment does not ensure regrowth, and relapse is always possible. 34-50% alopecia patients experience a spontaneous recovery in hair growth within a year [7, 49].

Drug	Mode of Action	Adverse Effect
Corticosteroids [7,50,51]	Suppression of the pro-inflammatory cytokines and expression of anti-inflammatory cytokines	Folliculitis, atrophy, telangiectasia, acneiform eruptions
Minoxidil [5,47]	Peripheral vasodilator	Dermatitis or pruritus
Methotrexate [7,52]	Inhibiting dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR)	Loss of appetite, headache

Sulfasalazine [5,7,47,53]	Prodrug activated to sulfapyridine and 5-aminosalicylic acid (5-ASA) act on T cells.	Gastro-intestinal distress, rash, hepatotoxicity, headache
Cyclosporine [5,7]	Inhibits calcineurine, prevents transcription of cytokines	High blood pressure, gum overgrowth
Apremilast [5,7]	Inhibits PDE4, reduce inflammation by increasing cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) levels	Weight loss, decreased appetite, insomnia
Anthralin [5,47]	Antimitotic	Swollen lymph nodes, skin staining (yellow-brown)
Anti-depressants [48,54-56]	Stress reduction	Acneiform eruptions
JAK inhibitor [48,57-60]	Down regulation of inflammatory cytokines	Risk of infections
Interlukin-2 (IL-2) [48,61]	Lowers lesional CD+8 count	Fatigue, local reaction at injection site
Platelet rich plasma (PRP) [48,62-65]	Reduce apoptosis of dermal papilla cells	Swelling, redness at injection sites
Parathyroid hormone-collagen binding domain [48,66]	Hair cycle stimulator	Hypercalcemia, localized irritation
Quercetin [48,67]	Reduction in inflammatory cytokines	Headache, tingling
Statins [48,68,69]	Inhibit lymphocyte function	Headache
Valproic acid [48,70]	Increase growth signaling pathways	Hair loss
finasteride / dutasteride [5]	5- α -reductase	erectile dysfunction
Spirolactone [5]	inhibit production of androgen	Gynecomastia
Cimetidine [5]	Anti-androgen	Gynecomastia

ii) Herbal Treatment

Alopecia areata can be treated in a no. of ways by various medical systems, such as allopathic, ayurveda or surgery. The majority of people use

herbal medicine to prevent or lessen undesirable side effects from allopathic medications. Several herbs are used to stop hair loss and promote hair growth, these are described below [5].

Common Name	Biological Name	Family	Parts used	References
Shoeblack plant	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> Linn	Malvaceae	Leaves & Flower	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
Giant Dodder	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> Roxb	Convolvulaceae	Stems	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
Maek	<i>Asiasari radix</i>	Aristolochiaceae	Roots & Rhizomes	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
African basil	<i>Ocimum gratissum</i> Linn	Lamiaceae	Leaves	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
Aloe Vera	<i>Aloe vera</i> L.	Liliaceae	Leaves	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
Ginkgo	<i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	Ginkgoaceae	Leaves	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
Coat button	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Compositae	Leaves	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
Shrubby Sophora	<i>Sophora flavescens</i>	Leguminous plants	Roots	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
Bitter Apple	<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i> Schrad	Cucurbitaceae	Fruits	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
Indian Spikenard	<i>Nordostachys jatamansi</i>	Valerianaceae	Rhizomes & Roots	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)
False Daisy	<i>Eclipta alba</i> L. Hassak	Asteraceae	Whole plant	(kuldeepsingh, 2016)

Shikakai	<i>Acacia concinna</i>	Mimosaceae	Leaves	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Meliaceae	Leaves	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Brahmi	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	Scrophulariaceae	Leaves	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Camphor	<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i>	Lauraceae Camphor	Leaves	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Cinnamon	<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i>	Lauraceae	Bark	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Lemon	<i>Citrus limon</i>	Rutaceae	Fruits	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Amla	<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Fruits	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Eucalyptus	<i>Eucalyptus sp.</i>	Myrtaceae	Bark	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Alfalfa	<i>Medicago sativa</i>	Fabaceae	Leaves	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Indian olive	<i>Olea europaea</i>	Oleaceae	Fruits	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Avocado	<i>Persea americana</i>	Lauraceae	Fruits	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Sandalwood	<i>Santalum album</i>	Santalaceae	Bark	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Ritha	<i>Sapindus mukorossi</i>	Sapindaceae	Dried fruit	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Bhringraj	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	Asteraceae	Leaves	(Pushpender kumar jain, 2016)
Greater Burdock	<i>Arctium lappa L.</i>	Asteraceae	leaves and root	(Skowronska W., 2021)
Indian pennywort	<i>Centella asiatica L.</i>	Apiaceae	leaves	(Saansoomchai P., 2018)
Indian Mulberry	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	fruits	(Susanti L, 2022)
Muskat root	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	Acoraceae	roots	(Park Sang Oh , 2015)
Shell Ginger	<i>Alpinia zerumbet</i>	Zingiberaceae	leaves	(Taira N., 2017)
Japanese flowering cherry	<i>Cerasus serrulata</i>		flower	(Zhang B., 2023)
Fragrant glory bower	<i>Clerodendrum fragrans</i>	Lamiaceae	leaves	(Anggraini I., 2019)
Indian coral tree	<i>Erythrina variegata</i>	Fabaceae	leaves	(Mustarichie R., 2017)
Guava	<i>Psidium guajava L.</i>	Myrtaceae	Leaves	(Ruksiriwanich W., 2022)

DISCUSSION:

Human existence is significantly impacted by hair, which serves as a statement of pride. Alopecia areata, an autoimmune condition causes patchy hair loss. Non-scarring type hair loss is the second

most prevalent form. The early transition of hair growth phase from anagen into the catagen, telogen, and exogen phases results in alopecia areata. Although its pathophysiology is not fully known. The collapse of immunological privilege is thought to be the cause of alopecia areata.

Alopecia areata can be treated with the allopathic method but to prevent undesirable side effects, several herbal plants are used. This article has covered hair cycle physiology, alopecia areata's pathology, and herbal plants potential over allopathic treatment.

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